

Cyclodehydration of ω -Aryloxyacetophenones by Polyphosphoric Acid. Part I

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ω -Aryloxyacetophenones have been prepared by condensing phenacyl bromide with the corresponding phenol in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone and their cyclodehydration has been studied under different conditions.

Recently it has been observed that lead tetra-acetate oxidation of flavan-3,4-diols (A) followed by acid treatment of the product (B) yields 2-aryl benzofurans^{1,2} (C).

This conversion can be used to find out the hydroxy pattern of the two aromatic nuclei in leucoanthocyanidins (flavan-3,4-diols), a group of important natural products. It can also be used to differentiate between flavan-3,4- and -2,3-diols and -2,3,4-triols, since the latter two cannot yield 2-aryl benzofurans under this condition³. But at present the method is of limited use for lack of reference compounds i.e. 2-aryl benzofurans.

Literature records several methods for the preparation of 2-aryl benzofurans^{3,4,5} of which cyclodehydration of ω -aryl oxyacetophenones seems to be a very convenient route for their synthesis⁶.

The formation of benzofuran nucleus by aromatic cyclodehydration requires a phenoxy acetaldehyde or phenoxy methyl ketone. The aldehyde or ketone is comparatively stable towards acid reagents and the presence of a strong *o*, *p*-directing ether linkage facilitate cyclisation.

* The numbering system will be that adopted by Patterson and Capell, *The Ring Index*, Reinhold, New York, 1940, p. 130.

1. Bokadia, Brown and Cumming, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3308.
2. Gramahow, Johnson and King, *ibid.*, 1958, 4040.
3. Kostanecki and Tambor, *Ber.*, 1896, 29, 237.
4. Kawai, Nakamura and Sugiyama, *Proc. Imp. Acad. (Tokyo)*, 1939, 15, 45; [*C.A.* 1939, 33, 5394].
5. Davies and Middleton, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1957, 569, and *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 823.

(Where R = H, alkyl or aryl).

The early literature records many instances in which 3-methylbenzofurans have been prepared by cyclisation of β -ketoalkoxy benzenes⁶, but for the analogous arylbenzofurans, nothing is recorded except that *w*-phenoxy acetophenone was not cyclised by ZnCl_2 , P_2O_5 , oxalic acid, H_2SO_4 , or Na^7 . Since cyclodehydration of several phenacyl phenyl sulphides afforded 2- and 3-substituted thionaphthenes⁸, Davies and Middleton investigated the cyclodehydration of some *w*-aryloxyacetophenones⁸ using polyphosphoric acid as a cyclising agent. They have studied the cyclodehydration of *w*-phenoxyacetophenone and the three *w*-tolylloxyacetophenones and observed that :

- (1) at 80° the normal cyclisation product i.e. 3-phenylbenzofuran is formed.
- (2) at 132° the rearranged product, 2-phenylbenzofuran is formed.
- (3) at intermediate temperatures a mixture of 2-phenyl- and 3-phenylbenzofuran resulted.
- (4) Lower yield of the 3-phenylbenzofuran at 80° has been reported if the time is reduced to one hour or at room temperature for several hours.

The 2-phenylbenzofurans yield a complex with 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone where as the 3-phenyl derivatives do not. The two isomers were thus differentiated.

w-Aryloxyacetophenones needed for the present work have been prepared by condensing phenacyl bromide with the corresponding phenol in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in dry acetone. The following aryloxyacetophenones have been prepared and their cyclodehydration has been studied under different conditions.

- (I) R = OCH_3 ; R' = H
- (II) R = H; R' = OCH_3
- (III) R = H; R' = CH_3

6. Chem. Rev., 1946, 36, 455.

7. Stoermer and Atenstädt, Ber., 1902, 35, 3560.

8. Branford, Davies, Gamble and Middleton, J. Chem. Soc., 1956, 4791.

Like the early observation, cyclodehydration of (I) and (III) at 80° afforded 3-phenylbenzofuran while the cyclodehydration of (I), (II), (IV) and (V) at 132° yielded the 2-isomer. In the case of IV and V the cyclodehydration at 80° also gave the 2-isomer with slightly lower yield while (II) gave a mixture of 2- and 3-isomer at 80° and at 80° the 3-isomer was the exclusive product but the yield was poor. Cyclodehydration of (III) at 132° has already been reported⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL

o-(2-Methoxy-phenoxy)-acetophenone. (2-Methoxyphenoxy)methyl-phenyl Ketone (I). Catechol monomethyl ether (12.4 g.), phenacyl bromide (20.0 g.) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (13.8 g.) were refluxed in dry acetone (50 ml.) with stirring for 4 hr. The mixture was then poured in water (500 ml.) and chilled. The resultant solid was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from ethanol as colourless long needles, m.p. 103.5-104° (yield 17. g.); lit.⁵ m.p. 104°.

2-Phenyl-7-methoxy benzofuran (IX). Polyphosphoric acid was prepared by mixing phosphorous pentoxide (42 g.) and phosphoric acid (20 ml.). It was heated at 132° for 20 minutes and then *o*-(2-methoxy-phenoxy) acetophenone (5 g.) was added and the heating

at 132° with stirring was continued for 2 hr. more. The reactants were then cooled, diluted with water and steam distilled. The steam distillate was extracted with ether and the product distilled under reduced pressure to afford a pale yellow viscous liquid. (yield 2.8 g.), b.p. 163-165°/3.5 mm.; $n_{D,4} = 1.0410$; (Found C, 81.2; H, 5.3; $C_{15}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 80.3; H, 5.4%).

2,4,7-Trinitro fluorenone derivative. 2-Phenyl-7-methoxy benzofuran (5 g.) in absolute alcohol (10 ml.) benzene (10 ml.) mixture was heated with slightly excess of 2,4,7-trinitro fluorenone (1 g.) in the same solvent. The precipitated complex was filtered and recrystallised from the same solvent to afford orange red needles, m.p. 168-169°.

3-Phenyl-7-methoxy benzofuran (VI). Polyphosphoric acid prepared from P_2O_5 (42 g.) and phosphoric acid (20 ml.) was heated at 80° for about 20 min. and then *w*-(2-methoxyphenoxy) acetophenone (5 g.) was added. It was then heated at 80° with occasional stirring for about 3½ hr. After cooling it was poured in water and steam distilled. The distillate was extracted with ether and worked up in the usual manner to yield an oily product which was vacuum distilled to afford a pale yellow viscous liquid. (b.p. 154-156°/3.5 mm) yield 3.0 g.; $n_{D,4} = 1.6249$. (Found C 81.0; H 5.5; $C_{15}H_{10}O_2$ requires C 80.3; H 5.4%) It did not form any complex with 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone.

w-(4-Methoxy-phenoxy)-acetophenone. (4-Methoxy-phenoxy methyl)-phenyl Ketone (II). Hydroquinone monomethyl ether (12.4 g.) and phenacyl bromide (20 g.) were refluxed in acetone in the presence of anhydrous K_2CO_3 (13.8 g.). It was then poured in water and the solid recrystallised from rectified spirit to yield colourless flakes. (m.p. 66-67°; yield 17.5 g.).

2-Phenyl-5-methoxybenzofuran (X). (a) Cyclodehydration of *w*-(4-methoxy phenoxy) acetophenone (5 g.) was carried out at 132° for 2 hr. as in the previous case. The product was steam distilled and worked up in the usual manner. The product on crystallisation from rectified spirit yielded fine needles.; m.p. 128° (yield 2.8 g.). (Found C 79.6, H, 5.3; $C_{15}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 80.3, H, 5.4%). With 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone it formed orange red needles, m.p. 135-136°.

(b) At 80°. After heating at 80°, for 3½ hr., the product was steam distilled. The distillate was extracted with ether and the solvent removed. A solid separated which after crystallisation from rectified spirit afforded 3-phenyl-5-methoxy benzofuran (X) (m.p. and mixed m.p. 128° (yield 25%).

The liquid portion was distilled under reduced pressure. (b.p. 180-183°/6.7 mm.) (yield 46%). It does not form any complex with 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone. It is 3-phenyl-5-methoxy benzofuran (VII). (Found C, 80.8, H, 5.5.; $C_{15}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 80.3; H, 5.4%).

(c) At 60°. 3-Phenyl-5-methoxy benzofuran (VII) (45%) was obtained. Some unchanged aryloxyacetophenone was also recovered.

w-*p*-Cresoxy-acetophenone. (*p*-Cresoxymethyl) phenyl Ketone (III). *p*-Cresoxyacetophenone was prepared by the usual method starting from *p*-cresol (m.p. 64.5 to 65°) (lit⁹. m.p. 64.5-65.5° and lit¹⁰. m.p. 68°).

3-Phenyl-5-methylbenzofuran (VIII). *o*-p-Cresoxyacetophenone (5 g.) was cyclodehydrated at 80° for 3½ hr. The product obtained after steam distillation was purified by distillation and obtained as a colourless liquid, b.p. 326°, lit.¹¹. B.P. 328-329° (yield 2.5 g.). (Found C, 85.3; H, 5.7; Calc. for C₁₅H₁₄O: C, 86, 0; H, 5.6%).

o-(α -Naphthoxy)-acetophenone (α -Naphthyl phenacyl Ether). (IV). α -Naphthol (14.4 g.) was refluxed with phenacyl bromide and anhydrous potassium carbonate (13.8 g.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) for 4 hr. It was then poured in water when a waxy solid was separated. On repeated crystallisations from ethanol it gave shining prisms, m.p. 68-69° (yield 13 g.).

2-Phenyl- α -Naphthofuran (XI). Cyclodehydration of α -naphthyl phenacyl ether was effected at 132° for 2 hr. followed by steam distillation to afford a solid. This was crystallised from ethanol as pale yellow crystalline substance, m.p. 111-112° (yield. 50%). (Found C, 88.9; H, 5.1; C₁₈H₁₄O requires C, 88.5; H, 4.9%). It yielded an orange red 2, 4, 7-trinitrofluorenone derivative, m.p. 171°.

Cyclodehydration at 80°. Cyclodehydration at 80° was done for 3½ hr. The product obtained by steam distillation was identified as 2-phenyl- α -naphthofuran., m.p. 111-112° mixed m.p. 111 (yield 25%).

The portion left after steam distillation in the flask was cooled, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. It was identified as unchanged oxyacetophenone by its m.p. and mixed m.p.

The corresponding 3-phenyl- α -naphthofuran could not be obtained.

o-(β -Naphthoxy)-acetophenone. (β -Naphthyl-phenacyl Ether) (V). It was prepared by the action of β -Naphthol on phenacyl bromide in the usual manner, m.p. 104°; lit.¹² m.p. 104-106°.

2-Phenyl- β -Naphthofuran (XII). Cyclodehydration of *o*-(β -Naphthoxy) acetophenone at 132° for 2 hr. yielded a pale yellow thick syrupy liquid b.p. 191-193°/4-5 mm. (yield, 60%); n_D^{24} 1.6770. (Found C, 88.5; H, 4.8; C₁₈H₁₄O requires, C, 88.5; H, 4.9%). Its 2, 4, 7-trinitrofluorenone derivative crystallised as deep red needles from absolute alcohol benzene mixture, m.p. 159-160°.

Cyclodehydration at 80°. Cyclodehydration of *o*-(β -Naphthoxy) acetophenone for 3½ hr. at 80° also gave thick syrupy liquid, boiling at 190°-193°/4-5 mm, (yield 50%), which has been identified as 2-phenyl- β -naphthofuran (XII). (Found C, 88.9; H, 5.0; C₁₈H₁₄O requires, C, 88.5, H, 4.9%). It also gave a derivative with 2,4,7-trinitrofluorenone which crystallised as deep red needles from absolute alcohol benzene mixture. m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above sample 159-160°. The U.V. spectrum was also identical with that of the above sample. However, the corresponding 3-phenyl- β -naphthofuran could not be obtained.

10. Kunokell, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 577.

11. Stoermer and Barthelme, *Ber.*, 1915, 48, 68.

12. Victor Fritz, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 3031.

Thus, it seems that the cyclodehydration of *o*-aryloxyacetophenones and its subsequent rearrangement depend not only on temperature, but also on the various groups present in the aryl rings.

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